

ISSUES BRIEF

POACHING AND ILLEGAL WILDLIFE TRADE IN NIGERIA

- Despite Nigeria's party status to the CITES agreement, weak enforcement and implementation of wildlife laws, corruption, limited state presence, especially in rural areas, and limited inter-agency coordination have reduced the effectiveness of conservation measures to halt poaching and illegal wildlife trade.
- The Federal Ministry of Environment, Nigeria, as a matter of priority, needs to address the rapidly increasing number of threatened terrestrial wildlife species due to overexploitation.
- A decrease in wildlife species (e.g., vultures) will increase zoonotic disease transmission.
- Strict enforcement of wildlife legislation and environmental governance needs to be adopted in Nigeria.

What is the issue?

The [World Wildlife Fund](#) defines poaching as a wildlife crime involving the illegal harvesting of wild species from their habitats without consideration for sustainability or ecological balance. [Wyatt \(2021\)](#) defines illegal wildlife trade as a multi-stage smuggling operation involving the trade of poached, collected, or harvested wildlife species.

Poaching and illegal wildlife trade pose significant threats to Nigeria's protected areas, challenging biodiversity conservation and diminishing the stability and adaptive capacity of ecosystems ([Lameed et al, 2025](#)). The [IUCN Red List of Threatened Species \(2025\)](#) indicates that 72 of Nigeria's terrestrial species are threatened primarily by overexploitation (14 critically endangered, 23 endangered, and 35 vulnerable). These include species like the [hooded vulture](#), [grey parrot](#), and black-bellied pangolin. These statistics reveal the immediate consequences of

poaching and illegal wildlife trade: significant population declines of terrestrial species in protected areas, disrupting trophic interactions and ecological balance.

[UNODC](#) 2020 study found that international demand for products further drives wildlife crime in Nigeria.

IUCN Classification of Overexploitation-Driven Threats to Nigerian Terrestrial Species (IUCN Red List, 2025)

Nigeria is a party to the CITES agreement and has enacted national legislation, such as the [Endangered Species \(Control of International Trade and Traffic\) Act](#). A 2021 [study](#) by the environmental Investigation Agency found that enforcement and implementation remain inadequate. Corruption, weak border controls, especially in rural areas, and limited interagency cooperation further undermine these acts. At the [operational level](#), there is limited cooperation and capacity among the task force.

As a result, traffickers face minimal risk of detection and prosecution and exploit insufficient monitoring to transport wildlife products. The trafficking chains are also highly complex, involving poachers, collectors, transporters, corrupt facilitators, and international buyers. Products are moved through hidden forest routes and official ports using forged permits and bribes ([EIA, 2020](#)).

In transboundary regions like the [Obanliku](#) border area in Cross River State, Nigeria, a combination of environmental vulnerability and socioeconomic challenges exists. Communities along the border frequently serve as both agents and affected populations. Their proximity to international borders and weak government control exposes them to risks from illegal trade actors who leverage unofficial trade corridors, challenging terrain, and poorly monitored crossing areas.

[UNODC 2024](#) reported that on the 12th May 2023 and 21st October 2022, 397.5kg and 376.4kg of pangolin scales were seized by the Nigerian Customs Service, respectively. Two people were arrested, and two people are still wanted in each of the seizures. This illegal trade is driven by the high demand for pangolin scales in ethnomedical practices, particularly throughout Asian commercial channels. These scales result from extensive poaching and wildlife trafficking in forested regions.

Again, in April 2025, the Nigeria Customs Service (NCS) and the [Wildlife Justice Commission \(WJC\)](#) arrested five individuals and confiscated [3.765 tons of pangolin scales](#) in Lagos. This figure estimates that more than 1,900 pangolins were killed. This is the largest documented pangolin-

scale confiscation worldwide in 2025. There is limited knowledge in the handling of confidential human intelligence sources among the Nigeria Customs Service ([UNODC, 2024](#)).

Pangolin (IUCN 2025)

[Pangolin Scales seized by the NCS in April 2025.](#)
©Nigerian Customs Service

The recent seizures of [36 African grey parrots](#) in 2024 and 7 in September 2023 by Nigerian customs, as reported by BornFree USA and [UNODC](#), highlight the ongoing threat from poachers and international trafficking. These incidents also reinforce the urgent need for improved ranger capacity and stronger wildlife laws in Nigeria.

The lack of capacity in Nigeria in the forensic analysis of wildlife and wildlife products is a limiting factor in wildlife crime investigations.

Why is it important?

The [IUCN Red List of Threatened Species \(2025\)](#) reports that 72 terrestrial wildlife species are threatened by exploitation. These wildlife species support trophic interactions, ecological balance, and the sustainability of ecosystem services. The decline in the population is affecting the predator-prey relationship and disrupting trophic interactions.

Species like the hooded vulture, listed as critically endangered on the [IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, 2025](#), help clean the environment by consuming carcasses that serve as breeding grounds for zoonotic pathogens. Reversing population decline will reduce the transmission of diseases such as rabies and brucellosis and promote greater stability in ecosystem nutrient cycles.

Pangolins help control [insect populations](#); not only that, they excavate burrows, which positively impact soil processes by turning over organic matter and supporting aeration. They also provide cover and thermal [refugia](#) for a variety of commensal species. Seed dispersal of plant species over long distances is often done by parrots through [stomatochory](#) (dispersal by mouth or beak) and [endozoochory](#) (dispersal by ingestion and excretion). Gorillas and elephants also help in seed dispersal and forest regeneration. The decline in their population will lead to losses in their ecological functions.

Addressing the rapidly increasing number of threatened terrestrial wildlife species in Nigeria, driven by overexploitation, is therefore essential to curb their impacts on ecosystems.

What can be done?

Establish a joint transnational investigation team to serve as the operational arm of the wildlife law enforcement task force, formally established in 2023. Appoint a senior Police officer to lead this team. Prioritize immediate implementation and ensure the highest level of attention from the government and policymakers.

Proper inspection and prosecution of offenders are essential to regulate poaching, illegal wildlife

trade, and trafficking effectively. Within the Federal Ministry of Justice, an Environmental Crime Unit should be established to collaborate with the Wildlife Enforcement Task Force in overseeing wildlife criminal cases.

Poaching cum illegal wildlife trade, as an organised crime, requires interagency cooperation (Nigeria Customs Service, Nigeria Police, [Nigeria Park Service](#), [National Environmental Standard and Regulations and Enforcement Agency](#) (NESRA) to crack down on the complex trafficking chains (poachers -> collectors-> transporters -> facilitators -> international buyers). It is essential that Nigerian Customs Service staff receive prompt training in the proper handling of confidential human intelligence sources, and that a centralized register for informants be established.

Collaboration in data sharing, for instance, between Nigeria and Cameroon, is essential to anti-poaching initiatives and the suppression of the illegal wildlife trade.

Increase conservation awareness through targeted media outreach by engaging the public directly. Initiate public health campaigns that encourage individuals to educate themselves about zoonotic diseases and to disseminate information about their risks.

Form community monitoring teams led by indigenous leaders now to combat poaching and trafficking.

Where can I get More Information?

IUCN 2025. [The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species](#). Version 2025-2.

[Born Free 2024](#). Endangered Grey Parrots Saved by Nigerian Customs Officers.

[World Wildlife Fund](#)

[Wildlife Justice Commission](#) (2025).

[Wildlife Conservation Society](#) Nigeria.